

Use of Diazoethane in the Synthesis of Isocoumarins. Part II*.

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Manuscript received 2 May 1978, accepted 22 February 1979

Some isochroman-1,4-diones have been prepared using appropriate diazoethyl ketones. They have been reduced by sodium borohydride to the related 4-hydroxy-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins.

WE have earlier reported^{1,2} the synthesis of 3-methyl- and 3-ethylisocoumarins starting from homophthalic half-esters by way of diazoketone using diazomethane and diazoethane respectively. Kapoor *et al*³ had earlier prepared 2, 3-dihydro-2-methylbenzo[b]furan-3-one by using diazoethyl ketone (*cf.* Bose and Yates⁴). Recently 4-hydroxyochratoxin A has been isolated from *Penicillium viridicatum*⁵ and has been shown to have the structure (I). *cis*-4-Hydroxymellein(II) has also been isolated from *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*⁶, the *trans* isomer being isolated from *Apiospora camptospora*⁷. It appeared desirable to develop synthesis of 3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarins and in this communication we record our results using diazoethane leading to the synthesis of this class of compounds.

- (I) $R_1 = \text{Cl}, R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{CH}_3, \text{CH}(\text{CO}_2\text{H}), \text{NH}_2$
(II) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$

- (III) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3, R_4 = R_5 = \text{OH}$
(IV) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3, R_4 = R_5 = \text{OCH}_3$
(V) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3, R_4 = \text{OCH}_3, R_5 = \text{OH}$
(VI) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = R_4 = \text{OCH}_3, R_5 = \text{OH}$
(VII) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = R_4 = \text{OCH}_3, R_5 = \text{OH}$

McDuggleby and Holt⁸ and Bhati⁹ had shown that *ortho*-substituted ester group reacts readily with a diazoacetyl group leading to isochroman-1, 4-diones. If in place of diazoacetyl group we use

$-\text{COC}(\text{CH}_3)\text{N}_2$ in the above reaction, a ready synthesis of 3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione resulted. Thus the acid chloride of 3, 4, 5-trimethoxy-2-methoxycarbonylbenzoic acid(V) was converted into the related diazoethyl ketone which on warming with dilute sulphuric acid afforded 6, 7, 8-trimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione(VIII) in good yield. 3, 4, 5-Trimethoxyphthalic acid(III) was prepared by formylation of methyl 3, 4, 5-trimethylgallate with

- (VIII) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$, (XI) $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$,
(IX) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$, (XII) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$,
(X) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$, (XIII) $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{OCH}_3$

N, N-dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride to methyl 2-formyl-3, 4, 5-trimethylgallate, followed by oxidation and hydrolysis. The derived dimethyl ester(IV) was then partially hydrolysed with 10% methanolic potassium hydroxide (1 mole) when the less hindered ester group was hydrolysed giving the half-ester(V). It may be mentioned that the phthalic acid(III) was obtained earlier by Fiest and Dschu¹⁰ by a different route starting from 3, 4, 5-trimethylgallic acid and chloral.

Similarly we prepared 7-methoxy- and 8-methoxy-3-methylisochroman-1,4-diones(IX) and (X) from the appropriate phthalic acid half-esters(VI)¹¹ and (VII)^{9,12} respectively. When these 3-methylisochroman-1, 4-diones(VIII), (IX) and (X) were reduced with sodium borohydride in methanol 3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarins(XI), (XII) and (XIII) respectively were obtained in moderate yields. Unfortunately these hydroxydihydroisocoumarins could not be dehydrated to the related 3-methylisocoumarins by various methods such as (i)

* An earlier publication³ may be regarded as Part I of the series.

by pyrolysis, (ii) by refluxing with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine and (iii) by refluxing with iodine in benzene. The possible reason which prevents the dehydration of these hydroxyisocoumarins could be regarded as that the hydroxyl group at 3-position and hydrogen atom at 4-position are in *cis* positions.

Experimental

All melting points and boiling points recorded are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were determined in Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer, model 237.

Methyl 2-formyl-3, 4, 5-trimethylgallate: A mixture of methyl 3, 4, 5-trimethylgallate (11.3 g), N, N-dimethylformamide (42.2 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (12 ml) was heated on steam bath for 8-10 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled, decomposed carefully with water and then made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution. This was extracted with chloroform, the extract washed with water and dried (CaCl₂). On removal of chloroform *methyl 2-formyl-3, 4, 5-trimethylgallate* was obtained as solid (7.5 g) which crystallised from methanol in colourless crystals, m.p. 84-85°. (Found: C, 56.1; H, 5.8. C₁₂H₁₄O₆ requires C, 56.2; H, 5.5%).

3, 4, 5-Trimethoxyphthalic Acid(III): An aqueous solution of potassium permanganate (4.5 g in 90 ml) was added gradually to a mixture of above aldehyde (5.1 g) and potassium hydroxide solution (25 ml; 10%) with shaking in one hour. The mixture was then warmed on water bath for 2-3 hours at 70° until the purple colour of the potassium permanganate disappeared. The solution was cooled, potassium hydroxide solution (15 ml; 10%) was added and heated further for half an hour under reflux. The mixture was filtered from manganese dioxide in hot condition and the clear filtrate was cooled and acidified with sulphuric acid (5N) when 3, 4, 5-trimethoxyphthalic acid (4.0 g) was obtained. This was crystallised from alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 175° (lit¹⁰, m.p. 175-76°). (Found: C, 51.1; H, 4.8. Calculated for C₁₁H₁₂O₇: C, 51.5; H, 4.7%).

3, 4, 5-Trimethoxy-2-methoxycarbonylbenzoic Acid (V): An ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (4.8 g) was added to 3, 4, 5-trimethoxyphthalic acid (3.8 g). The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for one hour, washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and dried (MgSO₄). On removal of ether, dimethyl 3, 4, 5-trimethoxyphthalate (IV) (3.8 g) was obtained, m.p. 65-66° (lit¹⁰, m.p. 64-65°). This ester (3.5 g) was refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide solution (7 ml; 10%) for 45 minutes. Methanol was removed, the residue diluted with water and extracted with ether to remove any unchanged di-ester. The aqueous layer was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to afford the desired *half-ester* (V) (2.7 g) which was crystallised from

benzene in colourless crystals, m.p. 125°. (Found: C, 53.1; H, 5.4. C₁₂H₁₄O₇ requires C, 53.3; H, 5.2%).

6, 7, 8-Trimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione (VIII): A mixture of the foregoing acid (1.4 g) in dry benzene (10 ml), thionyl chloride (2.5 ml) and pyridine (1 drop) was refluxed on water bath for 2-3 hours. This was worked up as usual to give the related acid chloride as oil. A solution of this acid chloride in dry ether was then added to a dry ethereal diazoethane prepared from nitrosoethylurea (5.0 g) and the mixture kept overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, ether was removed under reduced pressure at room temperature when an oily *diazethylketone* was obtained. This was decomposed by warming with dilute sulphuric acid (5N) on water bath until the evolution of nitrogen gas ceased. The resulting mixture was cooled to give 6, 7, 8-trimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione (VIII) as solid. This was filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene as tiny needles (0.8 g), m.p. 148-49°. (Found: C, 58.5; H, 5.1. C₁₃H₁₄O₆ requires C, 58.6; H, 5.2%). ν_{\max} (KBr) 1730 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl). The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared and crystallised from acetic acid as orange needles, m.p. 222-23°. (Found: N, 12.3. C₁₉H₁₈O₉N₄ requires N, 12.5%).

6, 7, 8-Trimethoxy-3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XI): A mixture of aqueous sodium borohydride solution (0.35 g in 10 ml) and sodium hydroxide solution (0.5 ml; 10%) was added dropwise to the stirred cold methanolic solution (15 ml) of 6, 7, 8-trimethoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione (VIII) (1.35 g) in 25 minutes. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, the excess borohydride was decomposed carefully with sulphuric acid. The mixture was extracted with ether, the extract washed successively with a saturated sodium bisulphite solution and water and then dried (MgSO₄). The removal of ether afforded 6, 7, 8-trimethoxy-3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (XI) (1.0 g) as solid which crystallised from methanol as colourless plates, m.p. 80-81°. (Found: C, 58.6; H, 7.5. C₁₃H₁₆O₆ requires C, 58.2; H, 6.7%). ν_{\max} (KBr) 3440 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl).

7-Methoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione (XII): 4-Methoxy-2-methoxycarbonylbenzoic acid (VI)¹¹ (2.1 g) was converted into its acid chloride in the usual manner. An ethereal solution of this acid chloride was added slowly to dry ethereal diazoethane prepared from nitrosoethylurea (8.0 g) and the mixture kept overnight. Next day, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford the related *diazethyl ketone* as thick yellow oil. This was warmed with sulphuric acid (20 ml; 5N) on water bath with frequent shaking for 40 minutes. The resultant mixture was cooled and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed successively

with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally dried (CaCl_2). Removal of chloroform afforded 7-methoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione(XII) as solid which was crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals, m.p. 135°. (Found : C, 63.7 ; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.1 ; H, 4.8%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1680 cm^{-1} (aromatic carbonyl).

The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared and crystallised from acetic acid as orange crystals, m.p. 205-206°. (Found : N, 14.1. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.5%).

7-Methoxy-3,4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin(XII) : The above isochromandione (XII) (0.5 g) in methanol (5 ml) was reduced with sodium borohydride (0.15 g) in water (5 ml) in the same manner as described earlier and worked up to give 7-methoxy-3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin(XII) as oil (0.2 g) which was distilled at bath temperature 180-90°/1.75 mm. (Found : C, 62.6 ; H, 6.9. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.8 ; H, 6.7%). ν_{max} (neat) 3390 cm^{-1} hydroxyl and 1730 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl).

8-Methoxy-3-methylisochroman-1, 4-dione(X) : The dry ethereal solution of the acid chloride of 3-methoxy-2-methoxycarbonylbenzoic acid(VII)^{9,12} (1.7 g) prepared in the usual manner, was added to dry ethereal solution of diazoethane prepared from nitrosoethyl urea (7.0 g) and the mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure when the related diazoethyl ketone was obtained as yellow oil. This was then warmed on water bath with sulphuric acid (20 ml ; 5N) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and the reaction mixture was worked up as usual to give the expected isochromandione(X) as oil. ν_{max} (neat) 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl) and 1675 cm^{-1} (aromatic carbonyl).

The 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative was prepared and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 195-96°. (Found : N, 14.2. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.5%).

8-Methoxy-3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin(XIII) : The above isochromandione(X) (0.5 g) in methanol (5 ml) was reduced with sodium borohydride (0.15 g) in water (5 ml) to give 8-methoxy-3, 4-dihydro-4-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin(XIII) as liquid which was distilled at bath temperature 190-95°/2 mm. (Found : C, 62.4 ; H, 6.9. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.8 ; H, 6.7%). ν_{max} (neat) 3460 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl) and 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl).

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